

Continental-scale evidence of farm management impacts on soil carbon

Julian Helfenstein¹, Nick van Dijk¹, Anna Edlinger², Gabriel Y.K. Moinet³, Sophie van Rijssel¹, Alexandre M.J.-C. Wadoux⁴, Rachel Creamer³, Carmen Vazquez³, Vera L. Mulder¹

¹ Soil Geography and Landscape Group, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands

² Wageningen Environmental Research, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands

³ Soil Biology Group, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands

⁴ College of Science and Engineering, James Cook University, Cairns, Australia

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ABSTRACT

There are high expectations that agricultural practices can mitigate climate change and improve soil health by increasing soil organic carbon (SOC). However, existing large scale SOC monitoring treats agricultural management as a black box, meaning that observed patterns and trends cannot inform on sustainable practices. Here, we for the first time combine management data from systematic farm surveys (n = 81,688 farms) and representative soil monitoring data (n = 8,834 locations) to quantify the impact of agricultural practices on three SOC metrics across Europe: stocks, stocks relative to pedoclimatic benchmarks, and yearly change in SOC concentration. Our findings show that management intensity is a significant contributor to SOC loss across Europe, with varying impact by soil and climate region. In turn, several practices (e.g. high share of manure, organic management, and a high proportion of leys in crop rotation) demonstrated potential for increasing SOC in different agricultural systems. This research opens new avenues for understanding leverage points to enhance soil health, and provides unprecedented evidence for informing policies promoting sustainable farming practices.

32 MAIN

33 Maintaining soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks in agricultural systems is critical for sustaining soil
34 health, and avoiding CO₂ emissions from degradation¹⁻⁴. Protecting existing SOC helps preserve
35 nutrient cycling, soil structure, biodiversity, and water regulation, all of which underpin productive
36 and sustainable farming systems^{5,6}. Increasing SOC stocks, defined as soil carbon sequestration⁷,
37 can also remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, but global sequestration potential is modest and time-
38 limited due to steady-states, reversibility, and socio-economic constraints⁸. Even optimistic
39 scenarios suggest it could offset only a small share of the emission reductions needed for climate
40 targets⁴. Nonetheless, optimal SOC management is a central component of sustainable soil
41 management and sits on the right side of the climate equation. A significant amount of research
42 has shown that the adoption of sustainable management practices such as diverse crop rotations,
43 organic amendments, or perennial cropping - among others - can slow or reverse declines in SOC
44 stock^{1,9}.

45 However, current understanding of management effects on SOC stocks mostly stems from
46 controlled field experiments⁹⁻¹¹, which reveal that both management effects on SOC and the
47 influence of SOC on other ecosystem functions are highly context dependent^{8,12}. Meta-analyses of
48 dozens of controlled experiments allow to isolate the influence of pedoclimatic variability, and
49 have shown that biochar applications, organic fertilizers, perennial crops, and agroforestry have
50 positive effects on SOC in a large majority of cases, while tillage intensity, crop rotation, and
51 mineral fertilizer application have smaller or more ambivalent effects^{1,13,14}. While these provide
52 important scientific insights, meta-analyses of controlled experiments do not capture the complex
53 interactions and variability of farming practices as observed in real farms across different pedo-
54 climatic conditions¹². This because management practices on controlled experiments differ from
55 on-farm reality, as single practices are emphasized for testing, ignoring that these practices often
56 come in bundles¹⁵. A recent synthesis of management practices (tillage, crop rotation and
57 fertilization) identified more than 285,000 possible management bundles¹⁶, the application of these
58 bundles is then further multiplied by the differing pedo-climatic conditions when considering the
59 outcomes in terms of SOC stock and stock change¹⁷.

60 Opportunities for large-scale assessments of SOC stocks have arisen through the increase in
61 national and continental soil monitoring¹⁸⁻²⁰. For example, analysis of changes in SOC stocks
62 between 2009 and 2018 from the European soil monitoring network LUCAS Soil, showed small
63 increases in SOC stocks, especially in grassland soils²¹. However, in this and other large-scale
64 SOC assessments²²⁻²⁴, agricultural management was not considered, therefore while we can
65 monitor the change in SOC stocks, we do not understand the role of agricultural practices. Clear
66 understanding of how management impacts SOC stocks, and how that varies with pedoclimatic
67 context, is essential for science-informed policy, e.g. defining sustainable management practices²⁵.
68 Thus there is an urgent need for empirical evidence on the impact of real-world management
69 practices on SOC stocks to inform policy and implementation efforts²⁶.

70 Assessments of management impacts on SOC under real farm conditions remain rare, primarily
71 due to two major challenges: limited availability of farm management data and the high complexity
72 of covarying factors (pedo-climatic conditions, social influence, economic lock-ins etc.). The first

73 challenge can be addressed by combining on-farm soil sampling with farmer interviews to
74 document management practices^{27–29}. The second challenge can be mitigated either by limiting
75 geographic scope to constrain variability, sometimes including a paired-site approach where
76 controls are adjacent to the studied practice^{5,12,30,31}, or by focusing on specific cropping systems
77 across broad pedoclimatic gradients¹⁷. However, both of these challenges demand labor intensive
78 approaches which restrict sample size and representativeness of earlier studies.

79 To address this knowledge gap, we combined standardized European farm surveys (Farm
80 Accountancy Data Network (FADN), n = 81,688) with large scale soil monitoring data to
81 disentangle the effect of farm management practices on SOC across all 27 European Union
82 member states plus the United Kingdom (Supplementary Figure 1). We first used FADN to predict
83 likely management practices at all agricultural sampling locations of the LUCAS Soil monitoring
84 program (n = 8,834)³². We then analyzed relationships between management and three SOC
85 metrics: 1) SOC stocks, 2) deviations from benchmarked SOC stocks, and 3) the change in SOC
86 concentration from 2009 to 2018—while taking variability in soil typology and climate into
87 account. We hypothesized that:

- 88 1. Permanent crops, grasslands, and extensive crops (e.g., temporary grasslands, forage crops)
89 are associated with more positive SOC outcomes than intensive crops (e.g., potatoes, sugar
90 beet or cereals).
- 91 2. Higher management intensity negatively correlates with SOC outcomes.
- 92 3. The share of manure in the fertilizer regime, crop rotational diversity, share of leys in the
93 crop rotation, and organic cultivation are positively associated with SOC outcomes, while
94 tillage intensity is negatively associated.
- 95 4. Pedo-climatic conditions significantly influence the relationship between management and
96 SOC stocks.

97 **Results**

98 **Variability in agricultural management across Europe**

99 Analysis of farm management data from 81,688 farms revealed that agricultural management
100 practices exhibited significant variability across Europe, both between and within regions. For
101 fertilizer regimes, total N and K inputs showed a similar spatial pattern, with highest average
102 application rates in NW Europe, while total P inputs were highest in northern Italy, NW and NE
103 Europe (Supplementary Fig 2a-c). The share of N, P, and K from manure followed a similar spatial
104 pattern for all three nutrients, with highest average values in alpine regions and coastal areas of
105 northern Spain (Supplementary Fig 2d-f). However, the proportion of K derived from manure was
106 consistently higher than that of N or P. Organic farming was most prevalent in marginal regions,
107 i.e. with climatic constraints such as in the very north and south or in mountainous regions
108 (Supplementary Fig. 2g). Crop rotational diversity was highest in eastern Germany and Czech
109 Republic (Supplementary Fig. 2h), areas known for large farm sizes. The share of ley and fodder
110 crops in the crop rotation was highest in Sweden, SE France, Portugal, and Italy (Supplementary
111 Fig. 2i). Tillage intensity was generally high, indicating the prevalence of conventional tillage,
112 with lowest values in eastern half of Germany, parts of the UK and France, and southern Portugal
113 (Supplementary Fig. 2j).

114 While spatial patterns in farm management across Europe have been described previously^{33–36}, our
115 study is novel in that the use of individual farm data enabled us to describe crop- and altitude-
116 specific management practices for each region. Andalusia, the southernmost region of Spain,
117 provides an example to illustrate crop- and altitude-specific differences in management practices
118 identified from the farm surveys. While the Andalusian average N input level is 73.5 kg N ha⁻¹ y⁻¹,
119 our approach uncovered that reported application rates range from an average of 0 for nuts to
120 220 kg N ha⁻¹ for strawberries, with also differences within a crop depending on altitude
121 (Supplementary Fig. 3). Similar intra-regional variability was observed for all other management
122 variables, with organic farming providing another striking example (Supplementary Fig. 3). In
123 Andalusia, only 6% of farms growing wheat below 300 m altitude (n = 191) were organic, whereas
124 67% of those above 600 m (n = 89) practiced organic farming. These crop-region-, and altitude-
125 specific management practices were used to predict the most likely management at each LUCAS
126 soil sampling location.

127 Of the 257 regions analyzed, our approach identified significant differences in agricultural
128 management in most regions, with 93% of regions showing significant crop and altitude specific
129 differences in N input, 92% in P input, and 95% in K input. Significant differences were further
130 observed in 98%, 97% and 97%, respectively of regions for the share of N, P, and K derived from
131 manure; 88% for organic farming, 97% for crop rotational diversity, 95% for the share of ley, 80%
132 for the share of forage, and 89% for tillage intensity.

133

134 **Relationship between land cover and soil organic carbon**

135 SOC stocks ($\chi^2 = 1608$, $p < 10^{-15}$), benchmarked SOC stocks ($\chi^2 = 184$, $p < 10^{-15}$), and the change
136 in SOC concentration between 2009 and 2018 ($\chi^2 = 143$, $p < 10^{-15}$) were all significantly dependent
137 on land cover. SOC stocks were highest in grasslands, followed by arable crops with high soil
138 cover such as temporary grasslands and fodder crops (Fig. 1a). SOC stocks were calculated using
139 a mass-corrected fixed depth approach (see method) taking into account variations in concentration
140 of SOC and bulk density. While the concentration of SOC was considerably higher in grasslands
141 than any arable crops, they also presented lower bulk density than arable crops (Supplementary
142 Fig. 4). Generally, soils under arable cultivation, including temporary grasslands, had significantly
143 higher bulk density than grassland or permanent crops (Supplementary Fig. 4). Some permanent
144 crops showed low observed SOC stocks (Fig. 1a and b), as a combination of low bulk density and
145 average to moderate SOC concentration (Supplementary Fig. 4). To account for SOC accumulation
146 potential, observed SOC stocks were benchmarked by dividing by “typical” SOC stock values for
147 that pedo-climatic unit³⁷. These benchmarked SOC stocks were highest in permanent crops, set
148 aside land and low intensity arable crops such as temporary grasslands and lucerne (Fig. 1b).
149 Lowest benchmarked SOC stocks were found in intensive arable crops such as potato and sugar
150 beet, which are associated with intensive soil disturbance and minimal crop residue return.

151 A majority of sites (55%) showed an increase in SOC concentration from 2009 to 2018, confirming
152 De Rosa et al.²¹. Additionally, we found significant differences between individual crops, with

153 most permanent crops and grassland types tending to have lower risk of SOC loss (Fig. 1c). The
 154 crops most likely to have SOC losses were potato, rye, oats, and triticale.

155

156

157 *Figure 1. Relationship between soil organic C (SOC) metrics and land cover. SOC stocks (a),*
 158 *$\chi^2 = 1545, p < 10^{-15}$), the benchmarked SOC stocks (b), $\chi^2 = 163, p < 10^{-15}$), and the change in*
 159 *soil organic C between 2009 and 2018 (c), $\chi^2 = 143, p < 10^{-15}$) were all significantly dependent*
 160 *on land cover. SOC and land cover data from LUCAS Soil. Only land covers with $n > 10$ are*
 161 *shown. Total $n = 6795, 6795, \text{ and } 6362$ respectively.*

162 Management effect on soil organic carbon

163 Mixed linear models with pedoclimatic zone as a random effect showed that management intensity
164 significantly affected all three SOC metrics (Supplementary Table 1). Management intensity was
165 calculated from fertilizer input, share of manure, probability of organic cultivation, tillage intensity
166 (arable only), and share of leys and forage in the crop rotation (arable only). SOC metrics in arable
167 sites showed the strongest response to management intensity (Fig. 2), with a very clear negative
168 effect of intensity on benchmarked SOC. Arable sites with low management intensities showed a
169 benchmarked SOC of 30% above the pedoclimatic typical values, while the most intensive sites
170 were 12% below (Fig. 2b). While management intensity of permanent crops had a slightly negative
171 marginal effect, management intensity of grasslands was positively correlated with both SOC
172 stocks (Fig. 2a) and benchmarked SOC stock (Fig. 2b). The rate of change in SOC showed the
173 same negative correlation with intensity index for all three land cover classes (Fig. 3c).

174
175 *Figure 2. Relationship between SOC metrics and management intensity. Marginal effects*
176 *calculated from linear mixed models with pedoclimatic zones³⁷ as random effect and intensity and*
177 *land cover class as fixed effect. The model χ^2 are 124 ($p < 10^{-15}$) for SOC stocks (a, $n = 6,776$),*
178 *113 ($p < 10^{-15}$) for benchmarked SOC stocks (b, $n = 6,776$), and 7.3 ($p = 0.007$) for the yearly*
179 *change in SOC concentration (c, $n = 6,346$). See supplementary table 1 for further model details.*
180 *Orange = arable, blue = permanent crops, green = grassland, and purple = all sites (no significant*
181 *interaction effect). Shaded areas show the 95% confidence intervals. The black horizontal line in*
182 *b) indicates the benchmarked value.*

183 Regarding the effect of individual management practices, N input had a negative marginal effect
184 on SOC metrics for arable soils, but a positive effect up to 300 kg N ha⁻¹ for grassland soils (except
185 for the change in SOC concentration which increased linearly with increasing N inputs) (Fig. 3).
186 This observed positive marginal effect of N input on SOC metrics for grasslands explains the
187 positive effect of management intensity overall (Fig. 2). The share of manure in the fertilizer
188 regime had a consistently positive marginal effect on SOC stocks and benchmarked SOC stocks
189 (Fig. 3b, g). The organic farming had consistently positive marginal effect on SOC stocks and
190 benchmarked SOC stocks (Fig. 3c, h), but no significant effect on the change in SOC concentration
191 for arable sites (Fig. 3i).

192 The share of ley and fodder crops in the crop rotation had the strongest positive marginal effect on
193 observed and benchmarked SOC stocks in arable soils (Fig. 3e, j). A slightly negative effect of
194 crop rotational diversity on SOC stocks (Fig. 3d, i) was likely due to rotations with a high share of

195 ley and fodder crops,—which tend to have lower diversity. Tillage intensity was not found to have
 196 a significant effect on any SOC metric (Supplementary table 3).

197
 198 *Figure 3. Relationship between SOC metrics and individual management variables. Marginal*
 199 *effects calculated from mixed linear models with pedoclimatic zones³⁷ as random effect and*
 200 *management variables as fixed effects. Panels a) to e) show marginal effects on SOC stocks, panels*
 201 *f) to j) on benchmarked SOC stocks, and panels k) and l) on the change in SOC concentration from*
 202 *2009 to 2018. Only management variables that had a significant effect are shown, thus some plots*
 203 *are void. Orange = arable, blue = permanent crops, green = grassland, and purple = all sites (no*
 204 *interaction effect). Shaded areas show the 95% confidence intervals. The black horizontal line in*
 205 *b) indicates the benchmarked value. Crop rotational diversity and the share of ley and fodder crops*
 206 *in the crop rotation only applies to arable crops, thus only orange lines. See supplementary table*
 207 *2 and 3 for model details.*

208 **Soil- and climate-specific management effects**

209 To test how management effects compared for different pedoclimatic zones, we calculated the
 210 difference in observed SOC stocks between the 10% most optimally managed and 10% least
 211 optimally managed fields per soil pedoclimatic zone. Optimal management was defined based on
 212 results from the mixed linear models (see Fig. 4 and methods for details), e.g. sites with high values
 213 for share of manure in fertilizer mix, organic farming, and share of leys in crop rotation. In arable
 214 sites, optimal management consistently had a positive effect on observed SOC stocks compared to
 215 suboptimal management, except for Atlantic arable sandy soils, which may be due to the low

216 sample size (n = 118) for this soil type (Fig. 4a). Interestingly, even central arable sandy soils, for
 217 which we observed little management variability, had a significant management effect, suggesting
 218 that these soils are particularly sensitive to management. The strongest effect was observed on
 219 Alpine and boreal soils, where the difference between 10% most optimally managed sites and 10%
 220 least optimally managed sites was $41.2 \pm 10.2 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$.

221
 222 *Figure 4. Pedoclimatic zone specific management effect on SOC stock as a function of management*
 223 *variability. A) arable, b) grassland, c) permanent crop. Management effect is defined as the*
 224 *difference between SOC stock observed on the 10% most optimally managed and 10% least*
 225 *optimally managed fields per soil pedoclimatic zone. Optimal management is defined as high*
 226 *probability of organic cultivation, high share of manure, low rotational diversity and high share*
 227 *of leys in the rotation for arable; high probability of organic cultivation, high share of manure,*
 228 *and intermediate levels of N input for grassland and permanent crops (see Fig. 4). Management*
 229 *variability captures how variable management is within the pedoclimatic zone and is calculated*
 230 *as the mean normalized standard deviation per management indicator. Error bars show the 95%*
 231 *confidence interval. See³⁷ for definitions and distributions of pedoclimatic zones.*

232 For grassland sites, four out of seven pedoclimatic zones had significant management effects, with
233 strongest effects observed for cold climate semi-natural loamy and clayey soils ($29.3 \pm 4.8 \text{ Mg C}$
234 ha^{-1}), Mediterranean arable loamy and clayey soils ($23.2 \pm 8.3 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$), and continental semi-
235 natural loamy and clayey soils ($23.1 \pm 3.6 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$) (Fig. 4b). For the other pedoclimatic zones,
236 the combination of practices defined as optimal management for grasslands in this study were not
237 found to correlate with higher observed SOC stocks. For permanent crop sites, a significant
238 management effect of 16.8 ± 7.7 and $15.0 \pm 3.3 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$ was observed for Atlantic and Central
239 arable loamy and clayey soils and Mediterranean loamy and clayey soils, respectively (Fig. 5c),
240 with no consistent effects for the other pedoclimatic zone.

241 **Discussion**

242 **Management impacts on SOC**

243 While current understanding of how different agricultural practices impact SOC is largely based
244 on analyses of controlled field experiments^{1,9,10}, our study is the first to leverage large-scale, real-
245 farm data to account for the complexity of farming practices and their interactions with diverse
246 soils and climates. Other studies using on-farm data at smaller spatial scales have also found
247 negative correlations between management intensity and SOC in arable soils, e.g. in the
248 Netherlands⁵ or Southern Sweden³⁰, which we show at the continental scale. The negative effect
249 of management intensity highlights the combined effect of various management practices that may
250 deteriorate SOC stocks.

251 A key advantage of our approach is that both the soil and farm management datasets used here was
252 designed to be representative^{18,32}, thus capturing the actual variability of soils and management
253 practices at continental scale—an aspect that has been largely absent from previous studies^{5,17}. The
254 outcomes of our research thus provide crucial empirical evidence to guide effective policy design
255 and practical implementation. For example, our analysis shows that the positive correlation of SOC
256 with organic farming¹⁴, share of manure in the fertilizer mix^{1,10}, high crop cover such as through
257 temporary grasslands and other perennial crops^{9,13}, and no effect of tillage intensity^{1,9} previously
258 shown for controlled field experiments also holds for real-farms across Europe. While controlled
259 experiments have shown that crop rotation positively impacts soil carbon storage relative to
260 monoculture^{1,38,39}, our study shows that, in practice, the composition of the crop rotation (e.g. high
261 share of leys or forage crops) is more important than diversity of crops per se.

262 Even less is currently known about management impacts on SOC in grasslands and permanent
263 crops⁹. Our results show that permanent crops were associated with higher benchmarked SOC
264 stocks compared to arable systems and were more likely to have positive ΔSOC over time (Fig.
265 2), supporting the potential contribution of tree crop systems for increasing SOC stocks^{1,40}. In
266 terms of sustainable management of grasslands, the positive correlation of fertilizer amount with
267 SOC (Fig. 3) adds important nuance to sustainability trade-offs and context-dependency of
268 fertilizer use, confirming similar patterns observed at the regional scale on-farm surveys in
269 England⁴¹.

270 While ΔSOC is potentially most interesting from a monitoring perspective, the noise to signal ratio
271 for ΔSOC is particularly high, which is a challenge faced by all SOC monitoring studies. This

272 becomes apparent when juxtaposing observed yearly Δ SOC rates with typical values of
273 measurement errors. While observed Δ SOC were on the range of $\pm 0.1 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2), ranges
274 also reported by other studies^{1,21}, the relative error in SOC measurement has been shown to be
275 22.1% using data from laboratory proficiency testing schemes⁴², i.e. $\pm 3.3 \text{ g SOC kg}^{-1}$ for a typical
276 cropland soil with 15 g SOC kg^{-1} . This means measurement errors are more than an order of
277 magnitude higher than expected management effects, presenting a considerable challenge for
278 monitoring change of SOC, e.g. for C certificates. Three ways to overcome this dilemma are
279 measuring Δ SOC over long time spans, with large sample sizes, or by using a model of SOC stock
280 with quantified uncertainty at each time step, which can then be used to infer Δ SOC and its
281 variance. It is also critical to stress that monitoring SOC, particularly for climate mitigation
282 outcomes, should include assessment of bulk density, which is itself sensitive to management
283 (Supplementary Fig. 3) and whose variation can prevent reliable deduction of changes in the
284 quantity of C in the soil⁸.

285 **Filling the gap of management data in soil monitoring**

286 While management practices have largely been overlooked in previous large-scale SOC
287 monitoring studies^{21,22,24,43}, our study addresses this critical gap and provides a blueprint for future
288 studies. Globally, soil monitoring initiatives are expanding rapidly, with major programs underway
289 or planned in Europe²⁵, China⁴⁴, India⁴⁵, Africa⁴⁶, and Australia⁴⁷. Our results demonstrate that
290 routinely reported farm-record data are powerful predictors of SOC dynamics, even without plot-
291 specific management histories. This opens a new avenue not only for monitoring of management
292 impacts on SOC, but also for understanding management effects on other soil properties relevant
293 for soil health.

294 **Identification of soils particularly sensitive to management**

295 There are two dimensions to site-specific soil management. The first is that different soils have
296 different potentials for SOC storage. The second is that different soils are differently responsive
297 to management. The first has been widely acknowledged through discussions on pedo- or soil-
298 scape zones, or soil districts, by science⁴⁸ and policy makers, e.g. in the European Directive on
299 Soil Monitoring and Resilience²⁵. The second dimension has been emphasized in discussions of
300 context-specific SOC dynamics^{8,17}, but until now has been supported only by piecemeal evidence
301 from limited field experiments or case studies. Our study provides the first continental-scale
302 empirical demonstration that these relationships can be quantified consistently across diverse
303 regions and agricultural land-use systems.

304 Our findings show that soils differ markedly in their responsiveness to management, supporting
305 the idea that site-specific strategies are necessary for effective SOC storage. This variation likely
306 reflects the soil's inherent capacity to store carbon—shaped by factors such as mineral surface
307 area—and its saturation deficit, meaning how close it is to that capacity, which together determine
308 its potential to gain or lose SOC⁴⁹. For example, soils with high clay content and moderate climate
309 may still offer room for C accrual via mineral association, whereas already saturated soils – often
310 in cool and humid regions – may be more vulnerable to C loss if degraded⁴³. For some pedoclimatic
311 zones, SOC showed little response to management despite substantial variability in practices,
312 likely as a result of other constraining factors or because agricultural practices not covered in our

313 study are more effective in these contexts. Understanding where soils are both responsive and at
314 risk could help prioritize interventions and identify high-opportunity zones for SOC-based
315 mitigation.

316 To optimize SOC management, future policy should (1) avoid blanket approaches that apply
317 generic guidance across regions, instead tailoring strategies to local soil and socio-economic
318 conditions, and (2) ensure that management data are systematically integrated into soil monitoring
319 schemes.
320

321 **Methods**

322 **Farm management data source and processing**

323 Individual farm management data was obtained for the years 2018-2020 from the Farm
324 Accountancy Data Network (FADN) through data access contract IFD 2023_06 with the
325 Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development of the European Commission. FADN
326 annually samples roughly 80,000 farms, representing a population of about 5 million farms in the
327 EU. The survey is designed to be representative in terms of regions, economic farm sizes, and
328 types of farming³². Type of farming refers to 14 classes ranging from ‘specialists cereals, oilseed,
329 and protein crops’ to ‘specialist olives’ to ‘mixed livestock’⁵⁰. While several studies have
330 demonstrated the potential of FADN data to inform on spatial and temporal patterns in agricultural
331 practices relevant for environmental performance on a case-study basis, e.g. in England⁵¹, Italy⁵²,
332 or Lithuania⁵³, analysis of agricultural practices using FADN data has not been done for the whole
333 of Europe, nor has it been combined with soil data.

334 We calculated the following indicators for each farm:

- 335 • N, P, K nutrient input in kg ha⁻¹ as the sum of mineral fertilizer plus animal-based fertilizer,
336 whereby the latter was calculated as livestock density [livestock units ha⁻¹] times the
337 nutrient excretion per livestock unit per year. While nutrient excretion is livestock
338 dependent, we assumed values for dairy cows, equating to 135 kg N, 19 kg P, and 139 kg
339 K dairy cow⁻¹ year⁻¹, because one dairy cow equals one standard livestock unit⁵⁴.
- 340 • Share of manure in the fertilizer mix as animal-based fertilizer divided by total nutrient
341 input.
- 342 • Organic or conventional farming.
- 343 • Crop rotational diversity as the Gini-Simpson index of arable crop areas per farm.
- 344 • Crop rotational composition as the share of each crop category (cereals, roots and tubers,
345 dry pulses, sunflower, rapeseed, other industrial crops, fodder legumes, maize, vegetables,
346 and leys) following Ballot et al.³³, with several modifications. First, while Ballot et al.
347 (2023) only included the most important crops, we included all reported crops. Second, we
348 classified other leguminous fodder crops and mixtures as fodder legumes rather than
349 temporary grassland due to the high percentage (> 80%) of legumes in that category.
- 350 • Tillage intensity was calculated as fraction of area under conventional tillage + fraction of
351 area under conservation tillage * 0.2 + fraction of area under zero tillage * 0⁵⁵. Since FADN
352 does not contain data on tillage, tillage data was acquired from EUROSTATS for 2016

353 (EUROSTAT, 2020). The data contains the areas of conventional, conservation, and zero
354 tillage for each NUTS2 region, farm size category, and farm type combination, allowing
355 for the calculation of 8087 unique values of tillage intensity. This data was combined with
356 the FADN dataset based on NUTS2 region, farm size, and farm type to predict farm specific
357 tillage intensity.

358 Since the exact location of each farm is not known, linking with the soil dataset was done based
359 on common NUTS2 region, altitude class (<300 m, 300-600 m, >600 m), and crop type. Hence,
360 management indicators were aggregated for every NUTS2 region, altitude class and crop type
361 combination, for which there were at least 15 farms in the dataset. Values for years 2018-2020
362 were used to account for annual variation. The cut-off of 15 farms was prescribed by the European
363 Commission to safeguard the anonymity of farms. Each management indicator was calculated
364 using weighted medians and weighted standard deviations using the sjstats package in R ⁵⁶.
365 Weights were calculated considering both the proportion of the crop in the total farm area, and the
366 proportion of the farm's crop area relative to the total area of that crop in the region (Eq 1).

$$367 \quad w_i = \text{sqrt}\left(\frac{\text{area}_i}{UAA_i} * \frac{\text{area}_i}{\text{total area}}\right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

368 Where w_i is the weight of each farm. area_i is the area of the crop on the farm and UAA_i is the total
369 utilized agricultural area of the farm. Total area is the sum of all crop areas for that crop ($\sum \text{area}_i$).
370 Weighing by the proportion of crop in the farms UAA increases accuracy of predicting crop-
371 specific management, and weighing by the proportion of crop grown on the farm relative to the
372 total area grown in the region accounts for the representativeness of the farm for the region.

373 To assess the performance of the disaggregation, i.e. to quantify if the disaggregation provided
374 more precise estimates of management than NUTS2 level averages, Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test
375 was used, a robust alternative to one-way ANOVA ⁵⁷. Chi²-statistic and p-value were calculated
376 for each management indicator per NUTS2 region. In the main text we report the percentage of
377 NUTS2 regions with a significant Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test ($p < 0.05$), i.e. where our
378 disaggregation based on individual farm data improved data resolution relative to regional
379 averages.

380

381 **Soil organic carbon data source and processing**

382 Soil data was derived from Land Use/Cover Area frame statistical Survey Soil (LUCAS Soil), the
383 European soil monitoring survey, for the years 2009/2012 and 2018. LUCAS Soil is a standardized
384 and systematic topsoil survey across the European Union and United Kingdom with roughly
385 22,000 sample locations, around half of which on agricultural land¹⁸. We calculated three SOC
386 metrics to provide an overview of the impact of management on SOC dynamics: SOC stocks,
387 benchmarked SOC stocks, and the change in SOC concentration.

388 SOC stocks were calculated using SOC concentration and bulk density data from 2018. A true
389 equivalent soil mass (ESM) approach was not possible in absence of depth-layered data on SOC
390 concentration and bulk density⁵⁸. To allow for unbiased comparisons of SOC stocks across land
391 uses that differ in bulk density, we adopted a mass-standardized fixed-depth (“pseudo-ESM”)

392 approach: we predicted a reference bulk density ($B_{d, \text{ref}}$) from edaphic covariates and used it to
393 compute 0–20 cm SOC stocks for all points, including those lacking measured bulk density (B_d).

394 Measured B_d was available for about a third ($n = 3,538$) of the sampling points across arable,
395 grassland and permanent crops. Using this subset, we first developed land-use-specific regression
396 models predicting B_d from a subset of the soil variables from the LUCAS Soil database. To avoid
397 multicollinearity, we selected edaphic properties that were uncorrelated between them, including
398 soil texture (percentage sand and clay), total nitrogen, pH, and mean annual precipitations (MAP).
399 We then evaluated all candidate combinations and compared models using AIC. The parameter
400 estimates were extracted from the best regression model (including pH, total N and the interaction
401 between sand and clay) and were used to calculate land-use-adjusted reference bulk density ($B_{d, \text{ref}}$)
402 for each sampling point of the whole dataset ($n = 10,523$). The reference bulk density was then
403 used to calculate SOC stocks as:

$$404 \text{SOC stock (Mg C ha}^{-1}\text{)} = B_{d, \text{ref}} \text{ (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} \times \text{OC (mg C g}^{-1}\text{)} \times 20 \text{ (cm)} \times 0.1 \quad \text{(Equation 2)}$$

405

406 Benchmarked SOC stocks were calculated as the observed SOC stocks divided by the pedoclimatic
407 average, or typical, values from Feeney et al.³⁷. Since our dataset was larger than the one used in
408 earlier work, 19% of sample points did not have an assigned pedoclimatic zone. For these missing
409 values, the pedoclimatic zone was predicted using a random forest classification model. The model
410 was fit using the ranger package⁵⁹ on the training data ($n = 8587$), for which pedoclimatic zone
411 was known. The model had 500 trees, a minimum node size of 1, and a mtry parameter of 3, and
412 the following predictor variables were used: SOC concentration, NUTS3 administrative region,
413 land cover, lithology, sand, silt, clay, aridity index, potential evapotranspiration, Köppen-Geiger
414 climate class, mean annual temperature, and mean annual precipitation. See supplementary table
415 4 for data sources. The out-of-bag error rate was 0.057.

416 The change in SOC concentration was calculated as the difference in SOC concentration for 2018
417 and 2009/2012, divided by the number of years²¹.

418 Data cleaning followed De Rosa et al.²¹. Firstly, organic soils with $> 160 \text{ g C kg}^{-1}$ were removed.
419 Since land use change (e.g. from grassland to cropland) has been reported to strongly affect SOC
420 dynamics²¹, locations which were not consistently the same land cover class (grassland, permanent
421 crop, or arable) were removed. Finally, change in SOC values that were $> 100\%$ relative change
422 from 2009 to 2018 or $> 3 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ absolute change were removed, because such large changes
423 imply either measurement uncertainty or soil movement²¹. This decreased sample size to 8,706 for
424 concentration of SOC in 2018, 6,795 for (benchmarked) SOC stocks, and 6,362 for change in SOC
425 concentration, respectively.

426

427 **Predicting farm management at every soil sample location**

428 Farm management data was linked to LUCAS Soil sample points in one of three ways, depending
429 on data availability. For sample locations where there were more than 15 farms cultivating the
430 given crop in the same NUTS2 region and altitude class in the FADN dataset, those farms were

431 used to predict the management indicators using Eq. 1. This approach could be applied to 73.6%
432 of LUCAS sample points. For the remaining points, the search radius for farms was extended by
433 ignoring altitude within the same NUTS2 region. In this way, management could be predicted at
434 additional 22.9% of points. If there was still no match, the geographically closest farms with the
435 same land cover class within the same country were used (additional 2.0%). A remaining 1.5% of
436 LUCAS points could not be matched with FADN data after all three steps, for which management
437 was set as NA. Since this approach allowed disentangling specific management regimes for 36
438 different crop and grassland types within each region and altitude class based on extensive
439 empirical data, it provides considerably more nuanced estimates of agricultural practices compared
440 to earlier studies that relied on regional or national averages³⁵ or did not differentiate management
441 between crops⁶.

443 **Management effect on soil organic carbon**

444 Impact of agricultural practices on SOC was assessed using mixed linear models with pedoclimatic
445 zones as a random effect and management indicators as fixed effects. Since SOC dynamics are
446 known to differ by soil and climate type⁹, mixed linear models were used because they allow
447 testing hypotheses while controlling for variability associated with different pedoclimatic
448 conditions, thereby improving the robustness and generalizability of the results.

449 Three separate linear mixed-effects models were fitted for each SOC metric. The first model
450 assessed the effect of overall management intensity, the second examined the influence of
451 individual agricultural practices across all land-use types, and the third focused specifically on
452 arable crops, including practices such as crop rotation that are not applicable to grasslands or
453 permanent crops. For each case, a full model incorporating all relevant management variables was
454 initially specified. Model simplification was performed using stepwise backward elimination of
455 non-significant terms via the *step()* function from the *lmerTest* package⁶⁰. The significance of the
456 final model was evaluated by comparing it to a random-effects-only model using likelihood ratio
457 tests (ANOVA). Marginal effects were derived using the *ggpredict()* function from the *ggeffects*
458 package⁶¹.

459 SOC stocks were log + 1 transformed, benchmarked SOC stocks were log-transformed, and change
460 in SOC was hyperbolic arc-sine transformed to better meet assumptions of normality.

461 The management intensity index was calculated as the average normalized intensity rank of
462 probability of organic farming, crop richness, crop rotational diversity, share of manure in the
463 fertilizer mix, nutrient input, tillage intensity, and share of ley and fodder legumes in the crop
464 rotation^{5,62}. Crop diversity (Gini Simpson and richness), nutrient input (N, P, K), and share of
465 manure (N, P, K) were represented by multiple indicators in our data. In these cases, the measured
466 indicator values were weighted so that each function received unit weighting on average, with
467 equal contributions from all constituent indicators⁵.

468

469 **Soil type-specific management effects**

470 Since sensitivity of SOC to agricultural practices is known to differ based on soil, climate and land
471 use⁸, we tested how management effects varied based on pedoclimatic zone. Management effect
472 was defined as the difference in SOC stock observed on the 10% most optimally managed and
473 10% least optimally managed sites per soil pedoclimatic zone. Optimal management was defined
474 based on the expected SOC stocks according to the linear mixed models, i.e. high probability of
475 organic cultivation, high share of manure, and high share of leys in the rotation for arable; high
476 probability of organic cultivation, high share of manure, and intermediate levels of N input for
477 grassland and permanent crops (Fig. 4, Supplementary Tables 1-3). Note that optimal management
478 was defined for expected impact on SOC stocks only, not considering agricultural production or
479 other environmental outcomes.

480 To account for the fact that significant management effects were more likely to be observed in
481 pedoclimatic zones with high variability in management, management effect was plotted as a
482 function of management variability. Significant management effects for pedoclimatic zones with
483 low management variability can be interpreted to denote particularly sensitive soils, since even
484 small changes in management are likely to significantly affect SOC stocks.

485

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629 **Supplementary info for:**
630 **Continental-scale evidence of farm management impacts on**
631 **soil carbon**
632

633 Julian Helfenstein¹, Nick van Dijk¹, Anna Edlinger², Gabriel Y.K. Moinet³, Sophie van Rijssel¹,
634 Alexandre M.J.-C. Wadoux⁴, Rachel Creamer³, Carmen Vazquez³, Vera L. Mulder¹

635 ¹ Soil Geography and Landscape Group, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the
636 Netherlands

637 ² Wageningen Environmental Research, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the
638 Netherlands

639 ³ Soil Biology Group, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands

640 ⁴ College of Science and Engineering, James Cook University, Cairns, Australia

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642

643 **Supplementary figures**

644

645 *Figure 5. Spatial coverage of farm management and soil property datasets. Data from the Farm*
646 *Accountancy Data Network (FADN, n = 81,688 for the year 2018) was used to predict farm*
647 *management and (a) shows the number of farm records per NUTS2 administrative region for 2018.*
648 *The European soil monitoring network (LUCAS Soil) covers around 20,000 sample locations, of*
649 *which 8,834 were on agricultural land and met our inclusion criteria (b).*

651 *Figure 6. Spatial variability in farm management based on 81,688 representative individual farm*
652 *observations from 2018. Maps show the area-weighted mean value of a farm management*
653 *indicator per NUTS2 administrative region. a) – c) total N, P, K input in kg ha⁻¹, including both*
654 *mineral fertilizer and manure; d) – f) the share of N, P, K respectively derived from manure; g) is*
655 *the prevalence of organic farming (% of area); h) rotational diversity measured as the Gini-*
656 *Simpson index –score close to one means high diversity; i) share of ley and fodder legumes in the*
657 *crop mix; j) tillage intensity, see methods for details. See Supplementary Fig. 1 for the number of*
658 *farms (sample size) in each NUTS2 region.*

659

661 *Figure 7. Variability of management practices within a region. Andalusia, southernmost region in*
 662 *Spain, is used as an example to illustrate crop and altitude specific management calculated for all*
 663 *NUTS2 regions in the EU. Error bars in the second column show the standard error of area-*
 664 *weighted medians. Sample size varies from n = 23 (potatoes at 300 – 600 m above sea level) to*
 665 *714 (cotton at < 300 m above sea level) farm observations per point.*

666
 667 *Figure 8. Relationship between soil organic C indicators and land cover. SOC concentration (a),*
 668 *$\chi^2 = 2475.5, p < 10^{-15}$) and soil bulk density (b), $\chi^2 = 440.3, p < 10^{-15}$) were significantly dependent*
 669 *on land cover. Only land covers with n > 10 are shown. Total n = 8,760 and 2,809 respectively.*

670 **Supplementary tables**

671 *Table 1. Linear mixed model to analyze relationship between SOC indicators and management*
 672 *intensity. Marginal effects are shown in Fig. 2 of the main text. The model χ^2 are 124.2 ($p < 10^{-15}$)*
 673 *for SOC stocks (n = 6,776), 112.9 ($p < 10^{-15}$) for benchmarked SOC stocks (n = 6,776), and 7.3 (p*
 674 *= 0.007) for the yearly change in SOC (Δ SOC) concentration (n = 6,346).*

variable	DoF	SOC stocks		benchmarking stocks		Δ SOC	
		F-value	p	F-value	p	F-value	p
intensity	1	8.66	0.003	7.79	0.005	7.28	0.007
land cover group	2	7.27	< 0.001	31.25	< 0.001		
intensity*(land cover group)	2	38.03	< 0.001	40.46	< 0.001		

676 *Table 2. Linear mixed model to analyze relationships between SOC indicators and management*
 677 *indicators, all. Marginal effects are shown in Fig. 3 of the main text. The model χ^2 are 378.4 ($p <$*
 678 *10^{-15}) for SOC stocks ($n = 6,776$), 365.3 ($p < 10^{-15}$) for benchmarked SOC stocks ($n = 6,776$), and*
 679 *30.4 ($p = < 0.001$) for the yearly change in SOC (Δ SOC) concentration ($n = 6,346$).*

variable	DoF	SOC stocks		benchmarkd stocks		Δ SOC	
		F-value	p	F-value	p	F-value	p
land cover	39	2.93	< 0.001	3.76	< 0.001		
land cover group	2	15.37	< 0.001	14.61	< 0.001	0.68	0.510
N fertilizer	1	0.64	0.423	0.91	0.339	0.15	0.694
(N fertilizer)^2	1	18.85	< 0.001	18.60	< 0.001		
N fertilizer*land cover group	2	40.81	< 0.001	38.09	< 0.001	3.55	0.029
(N fertilizer)^2*land cover group	2	12.97	< 0.001	12.35	< 0.001		
manure	1	30.39	< 0.001	30.18	< 0.001		
manure*land cover group	2						
organic	1	57.15	< 0.001	54.84	< 0.001	11.52	< 0.001
organic*land cover group	2					5.05	0.007

680

681 *Table 3. Linear mixed model to analyze relationships between SOC indicators and management*
 682 *indicators, arable only. In comparison to models from table 2, these models were fit to arable sites*
 683 *only, using also management indicators for arable farming, namely crop rotation diversity, tillage,*
 684 *and share of ley/forage. Marginal effects are shown in Fig. 3 of the main text. The model χ^2 are*
 685 *300.0 ($p < 10^{-15}$) for SOC stocks ($n = 4,504$), 298.8 ($p < 10^{-15}$) for benchmarked SOC stocks ($n =$*
 686 *4504), and 62.3 ($p = < 0.001$) for the yearly change in SOC (Δ SOC) concentration ($n = 4,326$).*

variable	DoF	SOC stocks		benchmarkd stocks		Δ SOC	
		F-value	p	F-value	p	F-value	p
land cover	28	3.76	< 0.001	3.66	< 0.001	2.26	< 0.001
N fertilizer	1						
(N fertilizer)^2	1						
manure	1	3.81	0.051	4.93	0.027	9.72	0.002
organic	1	8.73	0.003	8.56	0.003		
tillage	1						
rotational diversity	1	16.62	< 0.001	15.72	< 0.001		
ley_forage	1	90.01	< 0.001	87.48	< 0.001		

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689

690 *Table 4. Covariate data and sources.*

variable	unit	definition	source
MAT	°C	mean annual temperature	WorldClim ¹
MAP	mm	mean annual precipitation	WorldClim ¹
aridity	-	aridity index	Global aridity ² Global potential evapotranspiration
ETO	mm	potential evapotranspiration	²
Koppen	categorical	Köppen–Geiger climate classification	Global climate classification ³
elevation	m	meters above sea level	LUCAS Soil
WRB	categorical	World Reference Base soil groups	LUCAS Soil
parent_material	categorical	main lithological units	LUCAS Soil
other soil properties	various	clay, silt and sand content [%]; oxalate-extractable Fe and Al concentration [g kg ⁻¹]; pH measured in water; electrical conductivity [millisievert]; available P (Olsen's) [mg kg ⁻¹]; exchangeable K [mg kg ⁻¹]	LUCAS Soil

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692 **References**

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